

Changes in the microbiological quality and content of biogenic amines in chicken fillets packed using various techniques and stored under different conditions

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study was to determine the biogenic amines (BAs) formed in chicken breast meat packaged using different techniques (AP, Hi-O₂-MAP or VP) during the storage under different conditions (cold room or display case), to correlate the microbiological quality (TPC, LAB, *Pseudomonas* spp. and Enterobacteriaceae) of chicken meat with BAs formation and to assess the suitability of selected biogenic amines as indicators of chicken meat spoilage. The initial TPC of chicken fillets was 2.57–3.04 log cfu/g. Over time a systematic significant ($p \leq 0.05$) increase in TPC was observed to >7.5 log cfu/g (AP and VP; display case) determined on day 9. It was found that cadaverine and tyramine dominated in quantitative terms in chicken fillets, regardless of packaging technique and storage conditions (166.00 mg/kg in AP meat in cold room on day 9 and 175.03 mg/kg on day 9 in MAP meat in display case, respectively). Taking into account the BAI, high and significant ($p \leq 0.05$) correlation coefficients (from 0.51 to 0.95) were obtained with all analyzed indicators of microbiological quality. The concentration of cadaverine, putrescine contents or BAI can potentially serve as chemical quality indicator for freshness of chicken meat.

1. Introduction

Over the last 50 years global poultry production has increased rapidly and now poultry meat is the most-consumed meat species in the world (Pawłowska and Sosnowka-Czajka, 2019). The increase in the production of poultry meat and the desire to prolong its shelf-life cause the search for the new methods of its quality evaluation.

The evaluation of chicken meat quality is mainly based on its sensory and microbiological characteristics (Balamatsia et al., 2006, 2007). However, it is increasingly often proposed to determine certain chemical indicators, such as qualitative and quantitative analysis of biogenic amines (BAs), as an indicator for food safety and quality evaluation as an alternative to microbiological analyses (Ruiz-Capillas and Herrero, 2019). Packaging techniques, e.g. in vacuum or modified atmosphere, with refrigerated storage are widely used today in order to extend the shelf-life of meat (Bhat and Bhat, 2011).

Biogenic amines (BAs) are low molecular weight organic bases. They have an aliphatic, aromatic or heterocyclic structure. In food, BAs are mainly formed by decarboxylation of amino acids under the influence of endogenous or bacterial enzymes (Doeun et al., 2017). At high concentrations BAs may pose a toxicological threat to human health. For example, the consumption of high levels of histamine and tyramine together with food can cause migraine headaches, food intolerance or hypertension (Naila et al., 2010; Jairath et al., 2015). BAs naturally occur in food, usually at low concentrations, and their increased content may result from the action of endogenous but also bacterial enzymes during food storage or processing (Ruiz-Capillas and Jiménez-Colmenero, 2004; Gardini et al., 2018).

The formation of BAs in food is affected by a number of factors related to raw material, processing and preservation technologies as well as microbiological quality (Jastrzębska et al., 2016; Doeun et al., 2017; Ruiz-Capillas and Herrero, 2019). An increased risk of BAs

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formation concerns products where their precursors, free amino acids and microorganisms showing the ability to biosynthesize enzymes catalyzing their decarboxylation, are found. Therefore, poultry meat, because of its high content of free amino acids and the favorable environment for bacterial growth, can be a source of BAs in the human diet in case of its increased consumption (Triki et al., 2018).

Increased content of some BAs in food may also be an indicator of poor microbiological quality of the food product (Ruiz-Capillas and Herrero, 2019), including meat (Balamatsia et al., 2006; Ntzimani et al., 2008). An increase in the BAs content of the food product during the storage can be used to assess food spoilage process (Naila et al., 2010).

Fresh meat naturally contains spermine and spermidine. During the storage, the levels of histamine, cadaverine, putrescine and tyramine increase, the spermine content slightly decreases and the spermidine concentration remains stable (Ruiz-Capillas and Jiménez-Colmenero, 2004). The level of BAs in chilled poultry meat depends, inter alia, on the species of birds and the way they are reared (Lázaro et al., 2015), the type of muscle (Silva and Glória, 2002) and the packaging technique (Patsias et al., 2006; Gallas et al., 2010). It is therefore not easy to establish a generally applicable indicator which, on the basis of BAs content, would reliably predict poultry meat quality (Vinci and Antonelli, 2002; Ruiz-Capillas and Jiménez-Colmenero, 2004). A number of indicators have been proposed in the literature to assess the degree of poultry meat spoilage based, among others, on concentrations of cadaverine and tyramine (Vinci and Antonelli, 2002), putrescine and cadaverine (Gallas et al., 2010) or the sum of concentrations of tyramine, putrescine and cadaverine (Rokka et al., 2004; Fraqueza et al., 2012; Lázaro et al., 2015) and additionally histamine (BAI index) (Silva and Glória, 2002; Triki et al., 2018; Wojnowski et al., 2019).

The available results of the studies on the influence of the packaging technique on poultry meat quality in terms of BAs content and microbiological contamination are inconclusive. Therefore, the aim of this study was (1) to determine the BAs formed in chicken breast meat packaged using different techniques during the storage under different conditions, (2) to correlate the microbiological quality of chicken meat with BAs formation, (3) to assess the suitability of selected BAs as indicators of chicken meat spoilage.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Meat samples and experimental design

The study material was skinless, boneless fillets (*m. pectoralis major*), which were obtained from chickens from intensive rearing. The raw material was obtained and then packed in industrial conditions in three experimental series. In each series, the meat was obtained from a different slaughtering day. Three different packaging techniques were used: air packaging (PVC overwrap) - AP, high-oxygen modified atmosphere packaging - Hi-O₂-MAP (75% O₂ and 25% CO₂), and vacuum packaging - VP. The meat was packed as described by Chmiel et al. (2019). From each of the packaging techniques 24 packages were prepared, which amounted to 72 packages in total. Each of the packages contained two fillets with a total weight of about 500 g. The packaged raw material was stored in a cold room (2.2 °C ± 0.3 °C) for 24 h without light access, because in industrial practice meat is delivered by the meat plant to retail networks only after such a time from packaging. The initial quality of the raw material was therefore determined on 1st day of storage. For this purpose, the raw material from 2 packages of each of the packaging techniques was used. The rest of the raw material was divided into two equal groups and stored for the following days in different conditions, a cold room without access to light (2.2 °C ± 0.3 °C) or exposed to light in a closed, vertical display case (average temperature 3.5 °C), which was described in detail by Chmiel et al. (2019) and Chmiel et al. (2020). To assess the changes in the quality of the raw material on the 3rd, 6th, 7th, 8th and 9th day of storage, 2 packages of AP, Hi-O₂-MAP and VP from the cold room and 2 packages from the

display case were randomly selected. The left fillet from each package was used for microbiological analyses and the right one for the determination of biogenic amines content (BAs).

2.2. Microbiological analysis

Microbiological analyses included the determination of the total plate count (TPC) of aerobic mesophilic microorganisms (30 °C for 48 h; PCS, 2013) on Plate Count Agar (BTL, Łódź, Poland), lactic acid bacteria - LAB (30 °C for 72 h; PCS, 2002) on MRS (de Man, Rogosa and Sharpe Agar; Bio-Rad Laboratories, Inc., Hercules, CA, USA), count of *Pseudomonas* spp. (28 °C for 48 h; PCS, 2010) on KING B Agar with an addition of 5 cm³ CFC (a selective freeze-dried supplement containing cetrimide and antibiotics: fucidin and cephalosporin) per each 500 cm³ of sterile medium (bioMérieux, Marcy-l'Étoile, France) and count of Enterobacteriaceae (37 °C for 24 h; PCS, 2005) on Violet Red Bile Glucose Agar (BTL, Łódź, Poland) All the bacterial counts were expressed as log₁₀ of colony-forming units per gram of meat (log cfu/g). Methods used for microbiological quality determination were described in detail by Chmiel et al. (2020).

2.3. Biogenic amines content

Method used for biogenic amines determination was based on our previous reports in which the detailed statistical parameters of the method have been also reported (Świder et al., 2020). Biogenic amine index (BAI) was calculated by summing putrescine, cadaverine, histamine and tyramine levels according to Triki et al. (2018). Meat characterized by BAI > 50 mg/kg was classified as spoiled meat (Ruiz-Capillas and Jiménez-Colmenero, 2004; Triki et al., 2018; Feddern et al., 2019; Algahtani et al., 2020).

2.4. Statistical analysis

The One-Way ANOVA analysis of variance was used to determine the influence of time or conditions of storage or packaging technique on the chicken fillets quality (microbiological quality and biogenic amines content). The detailed testing was conducted using Tukey's HSD test (significance level $\alpha = 0.05$). The data was analyzed using STATISTICA StatSoft Inc. software ver. 10 PL (StatSoft Inc., Tulsa, OK, USA). Pearson's correlation coefficients were used to determine the relationship between BAs and bacterial counts.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Microbiological quality

Table 1 shows the changes in the microbiological quality of chicken fillets packed using three various techniques and stored in a cold room or exposed in a display case for 9 days. The initial (determined on day 1) TPC of chicken fillets packed in AP, Hi-O₂-MAP and VP was 2.57–3.04 log cfu/g. This indicates the acceptable microbiological quality of this raw material (Latou et al., 2014). Over time, regardless of the packaging technique and storage conditions, a systematic, significant ($p \leq 0.05$) increase in TPC was observed to approximately 6.5 log cfu/g (cold room) and approximately 6.8 log cfu/g (Hi-O₂-MAP; display case) and >7.5 log cfu/g (AP and VP; display case) determined on day 9 (Table 1). The maximum TPC limit for fresh meat according to Latou et al. (2014) and Lázaro et al. (2015) is 7 log cfu/g. This threshold was therefore exceeded on the last day (day 9) in AP and VP meat stored in a display case (Table 1). In the studies of Lázaro et al. (2015), the 7 log cfu/g level for aerobically packed chicken fillets was exceeded after 7 or 9 days of refrigerated storage, depending on how the chickens from which the meat was obtained were reared (conventional, free-range or organic).

The effect of the packaging technique on TPC was observed on days 1–8, during the storage in both a cold room and a display case (Table 1).

Table 1
Changes in the microbiological quality of differently packed and stored chicken fillets (mean ± standard deviation).

Bacterial counts (log cfu/g)	Packaging technique	Storage conditions											
		Cold room, day											
		1 (initial) ^a	3	6	7	8	9	9	6	7	8	9	
Total Plate Count	AP	3.04 aA ± 0.04	3.21 aA ± 0.06	4.45bA ± 0.12	4.64bA* ± 0.08	6.50 cA* ± 0.04	6.54 cA* ± 0.01	3.04 aA ± 0.04	3.12 aA ± 0.04	4.57bA ± 0.14	4.89bA* ± 0.05	6.75 cA* ± 0.04	7.68 dA* ± 0.06
	HI-O ₂ -MAP	2.78 aB ± 0.13	2.85 aB ± 0.12	3.78bB ± 0.03	3.89 aB ± 0.08	5.36bC ± 0.11	6.52 cA* ± 0.05	2.78 aB ± 0.13	2.88 aB ± 0.10	3.84 aB ± 0.02	3.90 aB ± 0.06	5.44bC ± 0.03	6.82 cB* ± 0.08
	VP	2.57 aB ± 0.24	2.63 aB ± 0.21	3.43 aB ± 0.39	3.67 aB ± 0.35	6.32bB* ± 0.13	6.51 cA* ± 0.04	2.57 aB ± 0.24	2.71 aB ± 0.18	3.54 aB ± 0.30	3.79 aB ± 0.18	6.53bB* ± 0.05	7.52 cA* ± 0.02
Lactic Acid Bacteria	AP	2.76 aA ± 0.06	2.79 aA ± 0.06	4.38bA ± 0.18	4.49bA ± 0.08	6.45 cA* ± 0.05	7.45 dA* ± 0.16	2.76 aA ± 0.06	2.81 aA ± 0.06	4.39bA ± 0.18	4.56bA ± 0.10	6.62 cA* ± 0.02	7.86 dA* ± 0.22
	HI-O ₂ -MAP	2.62 aA ± 0.04	2.68 aA ± 0.02	3.39 aB ± 0.34	3.46 aB ± 0.24	5.56bC ± 0.11	6.43 cB* ± 0.03	2.62 aA ± 0.04	2.72 aA ± 0.03	3.41 aB ± 0.30	3.61 aB ± 0.15	5.59bC ± 0.09	6.69 cB* ± 0.04
	VP	2.56 aA ± 0.17	2.61 aA ± 0.15	3.35 aB ± 0.11	3.45 aB* ± 0.06	6.18bB ± 0.03	6.52 cB* ± 0.01	2.56 aA ± 0.17	2.68 aA ± 0.13	3.48bB ± 0.07	3.60bB* ± 0.05	6.31 cB ± 0.11	7.13 dB* ± 0.13
<i>Pseudomonas</i> spp.	AP	3.21 aA ± 0.04	3.24 aA ± 0.04	4.38bA ± 0.25	4.53bA ± 0.11	6.16 cA* ± 0.05	7.51 dA* ± 0.07	3.21 aA ± 0.04	3.25 aA ± 0.04	4.48bA ± 0.24	4.67bA ± 0.06	6.79 cA* ± 0.13	8.46 dA* ± 0.03
	HI-O ₂ -MAP	2.76 aB ± 0.04	2.81 aB ± 0.05	3.52 aB ± 0.16	3.65 aB ± 0.16	5.57bB ± 0.16	7.15 cB* ± 0.08	2.76 aB ± 0.04	2.85 aB ± 0.02	3.58bB ± 0.15	3.74bB ± 0.11	5.67 cB ± 0.17	7.62 dB* ± 0.07
	VP	2.80 aB ± 0.07	2.86 aB ± 0.08	3.45 aB ± 0.06	3.57 aB* ± 0.02	5.47bB* ± 0.02	7.44 cA* ± 0.03	2.80 aB ± 0.07	2.89 aB ± 0.06	3.53bB ± 0.03	4.64 cA* ± 0.07	6.59 dB* ± 0.12	8.44eA* ± 0.03
Enterobacteriaceae	AP	0.95 aA ± 0.03	1.09 aA ± 0.05	0.94 aA* ± 0.05	2.52bA ± 0.11	2.71bA* ± 0.08	2.96bA* ± 0.11	0.95 aA ± 0.03	1.14 aA ± 0.18	1.66 aA* ± 0.22	2.45bA ± 0.12	3.28bA* ± 0.14	3.84bA* ± 0.14
	HI-O ₂ -MAP	0.45 aB ± 0.05	0.49 aB ± 0.05	0.39 aB* ± 0.08	1.82bB ± 0.13	2.67 cA* ± 0.12	2.87 cA* ± 0.12	0.45 aB ± 0.05	0.55 aB ± 0.05	1.06bB* ± 0.12	1.77bB ± 0.17	3.01 cA* ± 0.10	3.41 cA* ± 0.21
	VP	0.40 aB ± 0.02	0.67aB ± 0.09	0.95 aA ± 0.03	1.66bB ± 0.16	2.63 cA* ± 0.06	2.94 cA* ± 0.09	0.40 aB ± 0.02	1.01bA ± 0.09	1.10bB ± 0.15	1.87cAB ± 0.19	3.21 dA* ± 0.16	3.73 dA* ± 0.07

Lowercase letters (a–e) indicate that average values in rows with different letters are significantly different at $p \leq 0.05$. The letters refer to the differences between particular days of storage separately for cold room and display case.

Uppercase letters (A–C) indicate that average values in the columns, for particular characteristic, marked with different letters are significantly different at $p \leq 0.05$. The letters refer to the differences between packaging techniques in particular day of storage.

Symbol (*) indicate that average values in rows, for particular days of storage, marked with * are significantly different at $p \leq 0.05$. The letters refer to the differences between storage conditions (cold room and display case).

^a The results for the initial day 1 were included in both analyses for cold-stored and exposed meat.

Significantly the highest ($p \leq 0.05$) TPC was found for AP meat compared to Hi-O₂-MAP or VP meat.

Since day 7 (AP), 8 (VP) and 9 (Hi-O₂-MAP), meat stored in a display case was characterized by a significantly higher ($p \leq 0.05$) TPC level compared to that stored in a cold room (Table 1).

The use of Hi-O₂-MAP packaging delayed TPC growth above 7 log cfu/g by at least 1 day compared to AP or VP meat when exposed in a display case. The observed lower level of TPC in the raw material in Hi-O₂-MAP compared to AP meat was caused by the CO₂ content in the MAP packages, which was also noted by Latou et al. (2014). On the basis of microbiological data (TPC) in the study of Balamatsia et al. (2007) a shelf-life extension of 2, 4, and 9–10 days, respectively, was achieved by VP and two MAP gas mixtures (30% CO₂/65% N₂/5% O₂ and 65% CO₂/30% N₂/5% O₂) for chicken fillets compared to aerobically packed meat.

In case of LAB, the maximum level, 7 log cfu/g (Nychas et al., 2008) was exceeded on day 9 for AP meat stored in the cold room and on day 9 for AP and VP meat from the display case (Table 1). At high levels (> 6 log cfu/g) LAB may cause detectable (sensor) changes, leading to spoilage of meat e.g. off-flavors, slime-production, organic acids formation (lactic, acetic, etc.; Patsias et al., 2006). AP meat was characterized by significantly higher ($p \leq 0.05$) LAB count compared to Hi-O₂-MAP and VP meat from the 6th day of storage both in a cold room and a display case (Table 1). In addition, meat exposed for 8 and 9 (AP) or 9 (Hi-O₂-MAP and VP) days in a display case was characterized by a significantly higher ($p \leq 0.05$) LAB count compared to meat stored in a cold room (Table 1). Lactic acid bacteria particularly, *Lactobacillus* (*L.*) *divergens* and *L. carni*, can produce BAs. With the growth of LAB species tyramine has been mostly associated (Silva and Glória, 2002; Kim et al., 2005).

A significant ($p \leq 0.05$) effect of meat storage time, regardless of the packaging technique, both in the cold room and in a display case, on *Pseudomonas* spp. was observed (Table 1). During the storage in a cold room, meat was characterized by a significantly higher ($p \leq 0.05$) count of *Pseudomonas* spp. on days 6–9 (AP), 8–9 (Hi-O₂-MAP and VP) compared to day 1. On the other hand, significant ($p \leq 0.05$) changes in the count of *Pseudomonas* spp. during the storage in a display case were observed already from day 6 of exposure, regardless of the packaging technique (Table 1). Significantly the highest ($p \leq 0.05$) count of *Pseudomonas* spp. was observed in each type of meat samples on the last, 9th day of storage both in a cold room and in a display case (Table 1). On that day, the level of 7 log cfu/g for *Pseudomonas* spp. was also exceeded, which is an indicator of the end of shelf-life of meat (Nychas et al., 2008).

On almost each of the analyzed days of storage, regardless of the storage conditions, meat packed in AP was characterized by significantly higher count of *Pseudomonas* spp. compared to Hi-O₂-MAP and VP. On day 9, however, no differences in the count of *Pseudomonas* spp. between AP and VP meat were found (Table 1). Other authors have also found a similar growth rate of *Pseudomonas* spp. and LAB in raw meat packed with and without oxygen. According to Pavelková et al. (2014), *Pseudomonas* spp. count was similar in chicken breast fillets on day 9 of storage, irrespectively of packaging technique (AP and VP). In addition, there were no significant ($p > 0.05$) differences in the number of LAB between AP and VP chicken meat during the entire time of storage (18 days, 4 °C ± 0.5 °C). Chmiel et al. (2020) also did not find any significant ($p > 0.05$) differences in *Pseudomonas* spp. count in chicken breast fillets packed in normal atmosphere (AP) and in vacuum (VP) on the 8th day of storage in the display case. The AP and VP chicken breast fillets did not differ significantly ($p > 0.05$) in terms of LAB count on the 8th day of storage in a cold room.

Differences in the count of *Pseudomonas* spp. between meat stored in a cold room and exposed in a display case were observed on days 8–9 (AP and VP) and on day 9 (Hi-O₂-MAP; Table 1). In the study by Balamatsia et al. (2006) a *Pseudomonas* count of ca. 7.0 log cfu/g was reached for the chicken samples packaged in air after ca. 8 days of

storage. However, for samples under MAP the population of this group remained lower than 7 log cfu/g throughout the entire storage period, i. e. 17 days. In these studies, a different composition of the modified atmosphere was used inside the package with chicken breast fillets (30% CO₂ and 70% N₂), which undoubtedly hindered the growth of *Pseudomonas*. According to Patsias et al. (2006) *Pseudomonas* have been shown to produce significant amounts of putrescine and cadaverine. Barbieri et al. (2019) reported that *Pseudomonas* can accumulate also histamine.

Ntzimani et al. (2008) reported that the presence of Enterobacteriaceae in foods is typically related to the absence of good hygiene and safety practices. The initial (day 1) determined Enterobacteriaceae count was below 1 log cfu/g (Table 1). According to Balamatsia et al. (2006) this suggested the good hygienic conditions and safety practices applied at the poultry processing plant. Enterobacteriaceae count increased progressively with storage time, regardless of packaging technique and storage conditions (Table 1). Significantly higher ($p \leq 0.05$) count of Enterobacteriaceae, compared to day 1, was observed on days 7–9 during the storage in cold room (regardless of the packaging technique) and on days 7–9 (AP) and 6–9 (Hi-O₂-MAP) and 9 (VP) of exposure in a display case. Regardless of the packaging technique and storage conditions, the highest values were observed on day 9, while the Enterobacteriaceae bacteria count in chicken fillets remained below 4.0 log cfu/g during the whole storage time (Table 1). Until the 7th day of storage in a cold room and exposure in a display case, in most cases, AP meat was characterized by a significantly higher ($p \leq 0.05$) count of Enterobacteriaceae compared to Hi-O₂-MAP and VP meat. At the end of the raw material storage time, on days 8 and 9, no significant ($p > 0.05$) differences were found in the count of Enterobacteriaceae of meat packed in different techniques, regardless of storage conditions (Table 1). Significant differences in storage conditions were observed on day 6 (AP, Hi-O₂-MAP) as well on days 8 and 9 (AP, Hi-O₂-MAP and VP), with meat exposed in the display case having a significantly higher ($p \leq 0.05$) Enterobacteriaceae count (Table 1). Balamatsia et al. (2006) reported that chicken fillets packaged in MAP (30% CO₂ and 70% N₂) were characterized by a lower Enterobacteriaceae count compared to AP meat, up to 8 day of storage. Beyond this point in time Enterobacteriaceae population were almost equal for meat from both packaging techniques, reaching final counts of 7.5–7.6 log cfu/g. Enterobacteriaceae is the most common group that produced BAs in chicken meat (Balamatsia et al., 2006; Bunková et al., 2010; Lázaro et al., 2015). These microorganisms are considered to have a high decarboxylase activity, and consequently have been associated principally with the production of two of BAs, such as putrescine and cadaverine (Curiel et al., 2011).

3.2. Biogenic amines

The content of biogenic amines in chicken fillets during the storage (days 1–9), depending on the packaging technique and storage conditions, is shown in Table 2. No significant ($p > 0.05$) effect of both the storage time and conditions as well as the packaging technique on the spermine and spermidine content in the analyzed meat was found (Table 2). At the beginning of storage, spermine was the predominant amine, followed by spermidine. Spermine content ranged between 62.66 and 73.41 mg/kg and spermidine content between 11.18 and 18.38 mg/kg (Table 2). Both spermine and spermidine are amines naturally present in fresh meat, including poultry meat (Balamatsia et al., 2006, 2007). The reported amounts of these amines in the literature are wide-ranging (Rokka et al., 2004; Lázaro et al., 2015; Triki et al., 2018). Rokka et al. (2004) determined that the values of the spermine and spermidine remained constant for the first 12 days of chicken meat storage in MAP containing no oxygen (80% CO₂ and 20% N₂). On the other hand Ruiz-Capillas and Jiménez-Colmenero (2004), demonstrated that spermine and spermidine had a tendency to decrease. Balamatsia et al. (2006) found that spermine values were similar irrespective of packaging technique (MAP or air packaging), whereas for

Table 2
Changes in the biogenic amines content in differently packed and stored chicken fillets (mean ± standard deviation).

Biogenic amines content (mg/kg)	Packaging technique	Storage conditions (initial) ^a	Display case, day									
			Cold room, day									
			1	3	6	7	8	9	1	3	6	7
spermine	AP	69.36	71.59 aA ± 2.85	69.98 aA ± 2.60	69.02 aA ± 4.67	66.73 aA ± 1.94	64.45 aA ± 0.28	73.41 aA ± 4.42	70.07 aA ± 3.13	69.52 aA ± 5.93	63.59 aA ± 7.20	62.66 aA ± 1.74
		2.53	71.11 aA ± 4.38	72.20 aA ± 1.69	66.32 aA ± 2.93	65.79 aA ± 3.13	62.86 aA ± 1.41	71.23 aA ± 5.92	72.38 aA ± 9.37	71.59 aA ± 3.91	64.80 aA ± 4.67	63.39 aA ± 3.08
		0.38	70.75 aA ± 1.01	71.41 aA ± 3.56	69.16 aA ± 1.54	68.04 aA ± 3.64	66.27 aA ± 3.41	73.11 aA ± 5.76	72.68 aA ± 1.21	72.25 aA ± 2.12	69.34 aA ± 2.15	68.34 aA ± 4.67
Spermidine	AP	2.83	12.45 aA ± 1.63	13.28 aA ± 0.60	13.60 aA ± 0.31	12.78 aA ± 0.04	15.60 aA ± 0.64	11.18 aA ± 0.67	11.63 aA ± 1.17	12.38 aA ± 0.81	14.60 aA ± 0.85	13.05 aA ± 1.48
		3.54	15.28 aA ± 0.88	14.68 aA ± 1.73	15.08 aA ± 0.53	14.43 aA ± 3.15	16.48 aA ± 1.24	18.38 aA ± 4.07	16.13 aA ± 4.14	16.53 aA ± 1.17	13.60 aA ± 1.91	17.87 aA ± 2.17
		0.35	11.85 aA ± 0.71	12.93 aA ± 0.25	12.25 aA ± 0.21	14.20 aA ± 1.84	13.98 aA ± 0.88	13.25 aA ± 0.14	11.80 aA ± 1.77	13.23 aA ± 2.44	15.33 aA ± 3.48	13.82 aA ± 0.74
putrescine	AP	1.30 aA ± 0.21	4.22 aA ± 0.47	5.43 aA ± 0.95	12.30bA* ± 1.56	27.12 cA ± 3.01	28.18 cA* ± 2.23	6.01bA ± 1.10	14.64 cA* ± 0.48	19.13 cA* ± 1.94	31.10 dA ± 9.12	39.50 dA* ± 3.32
		1.03 aA ± 0.32	2.92 aA ± 0.80	3.00 aA ± 1.27	9.93bA* ± 0.88	13.70bcB* ± 1.77	18.53 cB* ± 1.38	3.55bA ± 0.57	6.28 cC* ± 1.66	15.38dAB* ± 2.23	22.43dAB* ± 4.63	33.88eAB* ± 4.35
		0.67	3.50abA ± 0.28	5.50bA* ± 1.48	11.40 cA ± 2.90	15.68 cB ± 1.66	21.13 dB* ± 2.02	3.88bA ± 0.53	11.30 cB* ± 1.13	14.53 cB ± 1.59	15.00 cB ± 4.38	27.25 dB* ± 0.78
cadaverine	AP	1.79 aA ± 0.23	7.13bA* ± 1.74	37.88 cA* ± 0.25	43.15 dA* ± 3.11	85.55eA* ± 18.88	166.00 fA ± 2.55	15.63bA* ± 2.58	49.03 cA* ± 7.18	82.03 dA* ± 16.16	143.85eA* ± 21.78	163.05eA ± 19.16
		0.0 aB ± 0.0	0.83 aB ± 0.10	14.40bB ± 2.05	30.30 cB ± 0.70	33.95 cB ± 1.63	70.33 dC ± 9.93	1.09 aB ± 0.0	18.78bB ± 0.88	32.83 cB ± 3.15	31.68 cB ± 5.69	81.33 dC ± 10.36
		0.38 aB ± 0.11	1.04 aB ± 0.07	8.70bB* ± 1.27	32.00 cB* ± 3.96	45.67 dB ± 6.27	117.14eB ± 22.36	1.08 aB ± 0.38	16.30bB* ± 4.74	43.45 cB* ± 2.69	49.85 cB ± 7.35	120.50 dB ± 13.51
tyramine	AP	1.65 aA ± 0.14	4.00bA* ± 0.49	36.08 cA ± 7.50	51.28 dA* ± 1.87	145.98eA* ± 14.54	1.65 aA ± 0.14	12.55bA* ± 1.70	42.65 cA ± 2.83	68.95 dA* ± 8.20	86.95eA* ± 3.46	175.03 fA* ± 19.91
		0.13 aB ± 0.04	4.63bA* ± 0.74	12.05 cC* ± 1.20	49.85 dA* ± 2.51	72.18eB ± 4.91	10.05bA* ± 2.33	16.53bB* ± 1.25	58.88cAB* ± 14.81	62.23 cB* ± 3.22	75.88 dC ± 0.11	
		1.38 aA ± 0.04	3.85 aA ± 1.98	21.70bB ± 3.82	38.43 cB ± 1.52	75.38 dB ± 5.90	131.83eA ± 7.32	4.35bB ± 0.64	22.83 cB ± 5.06	42.83 dB ± 4.07	81.90eA ± 4.38	142.18 fB ± 10.36
histamine	AP	0.38 aA ± 0.11	0.48 aA ± 0.11	1.43abA ± 0.18	1.83abA ± 0.18	2.10abA ± 0.16	2.65bA ± 1.27	0.75 aA ± 0.07	1.35 aA ± 0.28	2.65abA ± 0.99	3.08bA ± 1.24	2.80 aA ± 1.14
		0.25 aA ± 0.00	0.75 aA ± 0.14	0.93 aA ± 0.14	2.70 aA ± 0.71	3.45 aA ± 1.98	2.30 aA ± 1.06	0.90 aA ± 0.07	0.93 aA ± 0.95	5.33bA ± 1.59	5.23bA ± 1.52	4.80bA ± 1.13
		0.60 aA ± 0.35	0.63 aA ± 0.25	0.87aAB ± 0.17	2.28bA ± 0.11	3.37 cA ± 0.88	2.63bcA ± 0.11	0.92 aA ± 0.10	1.18 aA ± 0.18	2.70bA ± 0.21	5.98bA ± 2.09	5.35bA ± 1.91
tryptamine	AP	5.12 aA ± 0.47	15.83bA* ± 1.61	80.82 cA* ± 4.53	108.56 dA* ± 11.24	170.00eA* ± 19.86	342.81 fA ± 31.04	34.94bA* ± 5.44	107.67 cA* ± 5.11	172.76 dA* ± 8.91	264.98eA* ± 35.60	380.38 fA ± 21.44
		1.41 aB ± 0.28	9.13bB* ± 1.30	30.38 cB* ± 1.94	92.78 dA ± 16.61	102.98 dB* ± 0.39	161.34eC* ± 7.46	15.59bB* ± 1.53	42.52 cB* ± 0.42	112.42 dB ± 21.78	121.57 dC* ± 3.68	195.89eC* ± 15.73
		3.79 aA ± 0.25	9.02bB ± 2.58	36.77 cB* ± 3.44	84.11 dA* ± 2.69	140.10eA ± 12.96	272.73 fB ± 27.77	3.79 aA ± 0.25	10.23bB ± 1.16	51.61 cB* ± 8.49	103.51 dB* ± 8.56	152.73eB ± 5.27

Lowercase letters (a–f) indicate that average values in rows with different letters are significantly different at $p \leq 0.05$. The letters refer to the differences between particular days of storage separately for cold room and display case.

Uppercase letters (A–C) indicate that average values in the columns, for particular characteristic, marked with different letters are significantly different at $p \leq 0.05$. The letters refer to the differences between packaging techniques in particular day of storage.

Symbol (*) indicate that average values in rows, for particular days of storage, marked with * are significantly different at $p \leq 0.05$. The letters refer to the differences between storage conditions (cold room and display case).

Nd-below limit of quantification.

^a The results for the initial day 1 were included in both analyses for cold-stored and exposed meat.

spermidine lower values were obtained for chicken samples packaged in air than under MAP (30% CO₂ and 70% N₂). Also, levels of both these diamines decreased steadily with storage time.

The decrease in spermine content may occur because this polyamine is taken up from the media as a nitrogen source by microorganisms. In this study, only the tendency to reduced spermine content during the storage of meat in a cold room or display case was observed (Table 2). Spermine and spermidine were the only biogenic amines detected in meat at the beginning of the storage period. This may suggest that the development of microbiota with decarboxylase activity began only after that period, because other biogenic amines are produced by microbial action (Gallas et al., 2010; Triki et al., 2018). This was reflected in our study, as an increase (or significant increase) in the count of individual groups of meat microorganisms was observed after 6 days of storage (Table 1).

An increase in putrescine content was observed during meat storage, regardless of the packaging technique and storage conditions (Table 2). Significantly higher ($p \leq 0.05$) content of putrescine, compared to day 1, was observed during raw material storage in cold room on days 7–9 (AP and Hi-O₂-MAP) and from day 6 (VP). During the meat exposure in a display case, a significant increase in putrescine content was observed earlier, already on day 3, regardless of the packaging technique.

Meat packed in AP and stored in a cold room was characterized by a significantly higher ($p \leq 0.05$) putrescine content on days 8 and 9 of storage compared to Hi-O₂-MAP and VP meat. On the other hand, since the 6th day of exposure in a display case, VP meat was characterized by significantly lower ($p \leq 0.05$) content of putrescine compared to AP meat. Similar relationships were observed by Patsias et al. (2006). During the entire storage period in aerobically packaged precooked chicken samples significantly higher levels of putrescine were recorded as compared to MAP samples, regardless of the concentration of CO₂ (30–90%) and N₂ (70–10%). The influence of the packaging technique on putrescine content in meat is also indicated in the studies of Balamatsia et al. (2006), in which aerobically packaged samples were characterized by higher content of this diamine in comparison with MAP samples. Ntzimani et al. (2008) reported that the higher concentrations of putrescine in aerobically stored samples may be related to higher numbers of *Pseudomonas* spp. *Pseudomonas* are also responsible for the decarboxylation of amino acid lysine, which is present in significant amounts in chicken meat (Gálvez et al., 2020), leading to formation of cadaverine. According to Barbieri et al. (2019) putrescine can be accumulated with a single-step decarboxylation pathway by ornithine decarboxylase, common in Gram-negative bacteria (such as Enterobacteriaceae and *Pseudomonas*) or LAB. Triki et al. (2018) showed that the levels of putrescine in chicken meat during aerobic storage were mainly related to Enterobacteriaceae growth. Dainty (1996) pointed that the biogenic amines such as putrescine, cadaverine, histamine and tyramine are found in very low levels in fresh meat, and their formation is associated with bacterial spoilage. Such tendency was observed in our studies (Table 1). The higher concentrations of putrescine in AP meat in our studies may be related to higher numbers of *Pseudomonas* spp. in those samples as compared to a lower population of these species in MAP samples during the entire storage period. Enterobacteriaceae, which also produce putrescine, were present in significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) higher numbers in AP meat than in the MAP meat up to the 7th day of storage (Table 1).

There was a trend towards higher putrescine contents in meat exposed in a display case, compared to that stored in a cold room, but not in all cases these differences were significant (Table 2). In the last, the 9th day of the experiment, meat stored in a cold room, regardless of the packaging technique, was characterized by significantly lower ($p \leq 0.05$) content of putrescine as compared to meat from a display case. On this day, all the samples of chicken meat, irrespective of the packing technique, stored in the cold room were characterized by a significantly lower ($p \leq 0.05$) number of *Pseudomonas* spp. and Enterobacteriaceae (Table 1).

Cadaverine content increased steadily while meat was stored in a cold room or exposed in a display case, regardless of how it was packed (Table 2). A significant increase ($p \leq 0.05$), compared to day 1, was observed on day 3 (AP) and 6 (Hi-O₂-MAP and VP). Significantly the highest ($p \leq 0.05$) cadaverine content was observed on the last day of storage. The content of this diamine for meat AP, Hi-O₂-MAP and VP, when stored in the cold room, was 166.00, 70.33 and 117.14 mg/kg, respectively, and for relevant meat samples exposed in the display case in was 163.05, 81.33 and 120.50 mg/kg, respectively (Table 2). During the whole 9-day storage period, AP meat had significantly higher ($p \leq 0.05$) cadaverine content compared to Hi-O₂-MAP and VP meat, regardless of storage conditions. On the last day of storage, Hi-O₂-MAP meat was characterized by significantly the lowest ($p \leq 0.05$) cadaverine content, both during the storage in a cold room and in a display case. An increase in cadaverine concentration and its usefulness for characterization of fresh chicken meat quality was reported by Wojnowski et al. (2019). Balamatsia et al. (2006) showed a linear increase with storage time from 19.8 to 252.8 mg/kg for cadaverine level, in chicken meat stored at 4 °C for 17 days. Moreover, levels of cadaverine were higher in aerobically packaged chicken samples in comparison to MAP samples. Also Ruiz-Capillas and Jiménez-Colmenero (2004) and Min et al. (2007) found that cadaverine and putrescine levels increased during storage of meat.

Differences in cadaverine content in meat stored in a cold room or display case were observed on days 3–8 (AP) and 6–7 (VP). On the 9th day of the storage in a cold room, the content of this amine was similar for meat exposed in a display case, regardless of storage conditions (Table 2). As in the case of putrescine, the higher concentration of cadaverine in AP meat may be attributed to higher numbers of *Pseudomonas* spp. in these samples as compared to a lower population of these species in MAP meat. Silva and Glória (2002) reported, that putrescine and cadaverine were not detected in chicken meat until 10 days of storage and these could be due to the differences in the microflora of the meat samples. According to Baston et al. (2010) cadaverine and putrescine were detected beginning with the third day of storage of chicken meat. They were characterized by the highest values after a week of refrigerated storage. Putrescine together with cadaverine are identified as one of the toxic biogenic amines, as they favor intestinal absorption of histidine and tyramine and contribute to catabolism reduction, thus enhancing their toxicity (Triki et al., 2018). It was reported that putrescine, cadaverine and tyramine could be a quality indicators of chicken meat packed in MAP (Rokka et al., 2004) or aerobically (Min et al., 2007; Lázaro et al., 2015).

The effect of storage time both in the cold room and in the display case on the content of tyramine in the examined chicken fillets was found, regardless of the technique of packaging. Significantly the highest ($p \leq 0.05$) content of this aromatic amine was characteristic for meat on the last, 9th day of storage (Table 2). Rokka et al. (2004) reported high values of tyramine (130 mg/kg) for chicken cuts after 12 days of storage. The Authors attributed it to the high numbers of TPC (6–7 log cfu/g). In turn, in the studies of Balamatsia et al. (2006) levels of this amine in chicken samples stored aerobically or under MAP were low (<10 mg/kg) throughout the entire storage period (17 days) at 4 °C.

A significant ($p \leq 0.05$) influence of packaging technique and storage conditions on tyramine content was also found. However, the observed trends were not clear. On the 9th day of storage, both in a cold room and in a display case, Hi-O₂-MAP meat was characterized by significantly the lowest ($p \leq 0.05$) content of tyramine. Unlike in our study, Balamatsia et al. (2006) reported that tyramine levels were higher for chicken samples packaged under MAP as compared to those in air. However, there was no oxygen in the composition of the gas mixture used in MAP. In case of the storage conditions influence, meat exposed in a display case was characterized by a significantly higher ($p \leq 0.05$) content of this amine on days 3 and 7–9 (AP) and 3–8 (Hi-O₂-MAP; Table 2) in comparison to meat stored in a cold room.

A significant increase ($p \leq 0.05$) in histamine content was observed,

as compared to day 1, in meat stored in a cold room on days 9 (AP) and 7–9 (VP) and during the exposure in a display case on days 8 (AP) and 7–9 (Hi-O₂-MAP and VP). An increase in histamine content during meat storage was also observed by Ntzimani et al. (2008).

In this study, no significant ($p > 0.05$) influence of packaging technique and storage conditions on histamine content were found (Table 2). Balamatsia et al. (2006) found that the formation of histamine was only observed when Enterobacteriaceae had reached a population of ca. 7 log cfu/g after 11 days of meat storage. Moreover, lower histamine values were noted for samples packaged in air as compared to MAP samples. Naturally present polyamines (spermine and spermidine) along with putrescine, which is their precursor, may act synergistically toward formation of monoamines in chicken meat, including histamine (Patsias et al., 2006).

According to Triki et al. (2018), and Wojnowski et al. (2019) biogenic amine index (BAI) could be used for evaluation of the chicken meat freshness. BAI in our study showed a clear significant ($p \leq 0.05$) increase over storage time, irrespectively of packaging technique and storage conditions (Table 2). According to the index's classification, meat stored in a cold room showed signs of spoilage as early as day 6 (AP) and 7 (Hi-O₂-MAP and VP), and when exposed in a display case from day 6 (AP and VP) and 7 (Hi-O₂-MAP). However, this classification is not clearly related to microorganism levels on the same day of storage (Table 1). Min et al. (2007) also observed an increase in the BAI value during storage of poultry meat. In the study by Triki et al. (2018), a delay was observed in the formation of biogenic amines with respect to microbial growth which is in contradiction with the results obtained in this study. These differences could be caused by a different method of obtaining the raw material for research (meat purchased in the supermarket or meat obtained directly from the meat plant) and resulting high differentiation of the initial microbiological quality of the raw material, especially the level of Enterobacteriaceae bacteria. The above indicates that the relationship between BAI and the microbiological quality of the raw material is influenced by both its initial contamination and the type of microflora.

Meat packed in AP and stored in a cold room or exposed in a display case was in most cases characterized by a significantly higher ($p \leq 0.05$) BAI compared to Hi-O₂-MAP meat (Table 2). On day 9, regardless of storage conditions, Hi-O₂-MAP meat had significantly lower ($p \leq 0.05$) BAI compared to AP and VP meat. On that day no significant ($p > 0.05$) differences in BAI of meat stored in a cold room or exposed in a display case were found (AP and VP; Table 2). On the other hand, meat packed in Hi-O₂-MAP and stored in a display case was characterized by significantly higher ($p \leq 0.05$) BAI as compared to meat stored in a cold room.

3.3. Relationship between biogenic amines and bacterial growth

Correlation between microbiological counts and biogenic amines contents of chicken meat is presented in Fig. 1. The obtained correlation coefficients were different depending on meat packaging technique and the storage conditions.

The highest (> 0.80) correlation coefficients for AP meat stored in cold room were observed between TPC and putrescine and cadaverine (0.94 and 0.88, respectively) and BAI (0.86), LAB and putrescine and cadaverine (0.92 and 0.82) and BAI (0.80), *Pseudomonas* spp. and cadaverine and tyramine (0.93 and 0.90) and BAI (0.92), as well as between Enterobacteriaceae and putrescine (0.85). During the exposure of AP meat in a display case, the highest correlation coefficients were observed between TPC and tyramine (0.90) and BAI (0.81), *Pseudomonas* spp. and tyramine (0.86). A negative correlation between all bacterial groups and spermine content was also observed, regardless of storage conditions (Fig. 1). On the other hand, for Hi-O₂-MAP meat stored in a cold room, the highest correlation coefficients were observed between TPC and cadaverine (0.84), LAB and cadaverine (0.87) and *Pseudomonas* spp. and cadaverine (0.81), as well as between Enterobacteriaceae and putrescine, cadaverine and tyramine (0.90, 0.85 and

A)		Cold room						
		spermine	spermidine	histamine	tyramine	putrescine	cadaverine	BAI
Total Plate Count	AP	-0.70	0.39	0.71	0.77	0.94	0.88	0.86
	Hi-O ₂ -MAP	-0.49	0.42	0.23	0.68	0.68	0.84	0.76
	VP	0.24	0.46	0.67	0.94	0.89	0.90	0.93
Lactic Acid Bacteria	AP	-0.63	0.33	0.73	0.71	0.92	0.82	0.80
	Hi-O ₂ -MAP	-0.51	0.41	0.28	0.71	0.72	0.87	0.78
	VP	0.26	0.50	0.65	0.96	0.88	0.94	0.95
<i>Pseudomonas</i> spp.	AP	-0.66	0.61	0.64	0.90	0.75	0.93	0.92
	Hi-O ₂ -MAP	-0.46	0.44	0.17	0.66	0.64	0.81	0.73
	VP	0.16	0.38	0.44	0.89	0.77	0.93	0.91
Enterobacteriaceae	AP	-0.58	0.11	0.64	0.46	0.85	0.58	0.57
	Hi-O ₂ -MAP	-0.62	0.34	0.61	0.84	0.90	0.85	0.87
	VP	0.44	0.53	0.81	0.56	0.60	0.41	0.51

B)		Display case						
		spermine	spermidine	histamine	tyramine	putrescine	cadaverine	BAI
Total Plate Count	AP	-0.70	0.20	0.44	0.90	0.75	0.71	0.81
	Hi-O ₂ -MAP	-0.49	0.32	0.36	0.59	0.77	0.87	0.75
	VP	0.24	0.11	0.57	0.88	0.81	0.91	0.89
Lactic Acid Bacteria	AP	-0.63	0.29	0.27	0.77	0.71	0.68	0.73
	Hi-O ₂ -MAP	-0.51	0.30	0.42	0.62	0.82	0.90	0.78
	VP	0.26	0.09	0.65	0.84	0.80	0.91	0.88
<i>Pseudomonas</i> spp.	AP	-0.66	0.13	0.37	0.86	0.68	0.63	0.75
	Hi-O ₂ -MAP	-0.46	0.31	0.36	0.60	0.77	0.86	0.75
	VP	0.16	0.06	0.50	0.84	0.79	0.88	0.86
Enterobacteriaceae	AP	-0.58	0.61	0.69	0.52	0.70	0.77	0.67
	Hi-O ₂ -MAP	-0.62	0.22	0.53	0.71	0.90	0.92	0.85
	VP	0.44	0.50	0.84	0.63	0.47	0.48	0.57

values of correlation coefficients marked in bold are significant at $p \leq 0.05$

Fig. 1. Pearson's correlation coefficients between biogenic amines and bacterial groups: A) for storage in cold room; B) for storage in display case.

0.84) and BAI (0.87). During the exposure of Hi-O₂-MAP meat in a display case, the highest correlation coefficients were observed between TPC and cadaverine (0.87), LAB and putrescine and cadaverine (0.82 and 0.90), *Pseudomonas* spp. and cadaverine (0.86) as well as between Enterobacteriaceae and putrescine, cadaverine (0.90 and 0.92) and BAI (0.85). As for AP meat, a negative correlation between all bacterial groups and spermine content was also observed, regardless of storage conditions, but not in all cases these factors were significant (Fig. 1). Gallas et al. (2010) and Lázaro et al. (2015) also observed a negative correlation between spermine values and microbiological data. In chicken meat stored under MAP (75% O₂ and 25% CO₂), a negative correlation was found between spermine values and psychrotrophic bacteria counts (Gallas et al., 2010), while in chicken meat stored aerobically between spermine values and total aerobic bacteria and Enterobacteriaceae counts (Lázaro et al., 2015).

The highest correlation coefficients for VP meat stored in a cold room were observed between TPC and putrescine, cadaverine and tyramine (0.89, 0.90 and 0.94, respectively) and BAI (0.93), LAB and putrescine, cadaverine and tyramine (0.88, 0.94 and 0.96) and BAI (0.95), *Pseudomonas* spp. and cadaverine and tyramine (0.93 and 0.89) and BAI (0.91), as well as between Enterobacteriaceae and histamine (0.81). During the exposure of VP meat in a display case, the highest correlation

coefficients were observed between TPC and putrescine, cadaverine and tyramine (0.81, 0.91 and 0.88, respectively) and BAI (0.89), LAB and putrescine, cadaverine and tyramine (0.80, 0.91 and 0.84) and BAI (0.88), *Pseudomonas* spp. and cadaverine and tyramine (0.88 and 0.84) and BAI (0.86), as well as between Enterobacteriaceae and histamine (0.84). The reported correlation coefficients between amines content and microbiological indicator values in the literature are wide-ranging. For example, like in our study, Nassar and Emam (2002) found a positive correlation between putrescine and Enterobacteriaceae in chicken meat products. In turn, in the study by Ntzimani et al. (2008), the correlation coefficients between Enterobacteriaceae and putrescine and cadaverine were 0.70 and 0.33, respectively. A negative correlation between tyramine content and Enterobacteriaceae (-0.73) was observed in the study by Lázaro et al. (2015).

4. Conclusions

Biogenic amines such as cadaverine and tyramine dominated in quantitative terms in chicken fillets, regardless of packaging technique and storage conditions. With the storage time, the content of putrescine, and to a lesser extent histamine, also increased. On the basis of the values of correlation coefficients between the bacterial groups and the

concentration of particular BAs, it was found that the most useful for the evaluation of chicken meat freshness would be the determination of cadaverine, putrescine contents or BAI. The BAI value for the raw material packed in Hi-O₂-MAP was at the lowest level, compared to AP and VP, regardless of storage conditions. The BAI value for chicken meat packed using this method exceeded 50 mg/kg on the 7th day of storage, both in the cold room and in the display case. Therefore, from the point of view of product stability, this should be the preferred packaging method of the chicken fillets by meat processing plants. Moreover, the research results indicate that it is advisable to store the meat initially in a cold room and exposure it in display cases only for a short time necessary for its sale.

Our research also indicates that the concentration of biogenic amines can potentially serve as chemical quality indicator for freshness of poultry meat as the BAI level >50 mg/kg was reached earlier than the level of microbial contamination indicating spoilage of the meat (regardless of packaging and storage conditions). Further studies should be carried out to better understand of relationship between the level of biogenic amines and the level of microbial contamination, taking into account meat sensory quality.

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